

PIRLS ASSESSMENT SYSTEM CRITERIA.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7337392>

Research objective :In our country, in addition to current issues of state and societal importance, special attention is being paid to the issue of improving the quality of education and adequate preparation for international assessment processes. Successful participation in international assessment programs is directly related to improving the quality of education.

Research content: Participation in it, not only in Uzbekistan, but also in the world community, is considered an important tool in moving from assessing whether students have memorized the curriculum to assessing their competencies, that is, their ability to apply the knowledge they have acquired at school in real life situations, to develop creative and logical thinking skills, and to evaluate it. In addition, teachers are required to enrich students' imaginations about PIRLS research, increase the level of preparation for international studies, develop students' creative and logical thinking skills, thereby contributing to the improvement of the quality of education, in cooperation with the Education Inspectorate, the National Center under it, and experts in the public education system. is being implemented.

The PIRLS international study is a series of studies that determine the level of development of reading comprehension skills of primary school students, allow for international comparison, and can serve the state policy in the field of education in improving reading and teaching. is a major international evaluation program that provides analysis. Currently, PIRLS defines reading literacy as the ability to understand and use forms of written language that are required and valued by society, as well as the ability to make meaning from texts in a variety of ways. Research focuses on demonstrating understanding of how to apply knowledge to new projects and situations. The following criteria are set for the texts used in the PIRLS study: Text length: up to 1000 words, but for countries with low reading literacy, 400-500 words are set.

Topic: 1) Literary texts have a main theme, which is summarized by the reader in addition to the given text. 2) Informative texts cover a topic that is not taken from educational materials.

Language: The episodes are translated into more than 40 languages, so it is important that the translation is comfortable. Clear descriptive words such as metaphor or epithet are chosen. No colloquial vocabulary or jargon is used. Excessive technical means are not used. Content: The content of the text should be suitable for the age characteristics of students aged 9-10. Avoiding topics that are very specific to certain cultures is the main requirement of the research. The text should be interesting and enjoyable for school students of this age, and well written and not too familiar. It should be about a non-topic. Connection and sequence: It is important to follow the logical structure of the plot. Ensure the same use of simple and complex sentences in the text, if the dialogue dominates, combine information and add complex sentences. In the informational text, it is necessary to observe the structure of the text and the logical sequence of the information in relation to the visual elements such as titles, tables, and graphics. creates, observes the text, and consciously selects effective reading strategies. Each type of text follows typical patterns and rules to help the reader interpret the text. Any text can have different forms. These include traditional books, magazines, documents, and newspapers, as well as written forms in digital form. These processes, which are carried out on the basis of this program, should be carried out directly with disciplines and in an interdisciplinary way.

The reader is an active participant in this process, creating meaning, reflecting on the text, and consciously choosing effective reading strategies. Each type of text follows typical patterns and rules to help the reader interpret the text. Any text can have different forms. These include traditional books, magazines, documents and newspapers as well as written forms in digital form.

The PIRLS international study provides an international comparison of information on the level of development of reading comprehension skills of primary school students, which can serve public policy in the field of education to improve reading and teaching. provides analysis. Currently, PIRLS defines reading literacy as the ability to understand and use forms of written language that are required and valued by society, as well as the ability to make meaning from texts in a variety of ways.

In particular, PIRLS focuses on two overarching goals in assessing elementary school students' learning in and out of the classroom, namely, "acquiring artistic experience" and "acquiring and using information." In turn, each of these goals integrates four broad comprehension processes:

- *concentrate and find clearly indicated information;
- *making direct conclusions;

*evaluation and criticism of content and text elements;

*interpreting and combining ideas and information.

Currently, all research materials for the processes conducted in Uzbek, Russian and Karakalpak languages by the National Center for the Evaluation of Education Quality under the inspectorate: evaluation notebooks and questionnaires have been translated into relevant languages and received international certification. conducted.

The main PIRLS survey is a paper-based survey in which 4th grade students complete a test that assesses their reading comprehension levels and the student's personal opinions about their educational interests and home and school environment. fill out the questionnaire.

Also, the principals of the participating schools and the selected class leaders completed the school and teacher questionnaires examining the educational environment in the educational institution, and the parents or guardians of the students completed the home survey examining the educational conditions of their children. fill out the application form.

References:

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